

Examining the Impact of Servant Leadership on Service Quality: Exploring the Mediating Role of Service Climate in the Fast food Chains of Lahore Pakistan

Saqib Rehman¹, Nadia Noor²

¹Assistant Professor, Management Department, Lahore College for Women University (LCWU), Lahore.

²Assistant Professor, Management Department, Lahore College for Women University (LCWU), Lahore.

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Abstract

This research explores the realm of service quality in Pakistan's fast food sector, focusing specifically on the impact of servant leadership and exploring the intermediary role of service climate. The fast food industry in Pakistan, a robust and competitive market segment, emphasizes the vital role of service quality as a key differentiator. The study thoroughly investigates the correlation between servant leadership and service quality, and delves into the complex role of service climate as a mediating factor, shedding light on how servant leadership affects service quality. The aim of this study is to offer insightful contributions that could aid the fast food industry in Pakistan and advance the understanding of leadership in service-centric businesses.

Keywords: Servant Leadership, Service Climate, Service Quality

Introduction

The landscape of fast food chains is continually expanding, with these service providers immersing themselves in an increasingly fierce and competitive market. Setting themselves apart from the competition hinges significantly on the quality of the services, they deliver. Consequently, it is imperative to focus on evaluating service quality and customer satisfaction to gauge an organization's overall performance and benefits (Alqhaiwi & Luu, 2023).

Service quality is characterized by the gap between what customers expect and what they actually experience regarding the service provided (Grönross, 1990). This concept includes both physical aspects like the environment and design of a service space, as well as intangible elements such as the level of customer attention, efficiency of service, and the personalized experience offered by a business (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988). Notably, these intangible factors are often seen as a source of enduring competitive edge (Kuei, 1999; Salvador, 2004). While tangible attributes tend to be similar among competing entities, it's the intangible qualities, forged in each unique service encounter, that can significantly differentiate a business from its competitors. Fundamentally, the success of a service-focused business is heavily reliant on the performance of its frontline staff (Davidson, 2003; Tsaur & Lin, 2004; Alqhaiwi & Luu, 2023).

This research aims to examine the impact of servant leadership on service quality within Pakistan's

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fast food establishments and concurrently assess how the service climate acts as a mediator. The goal is to gain insights into how leadership approaches and organizational environment collectively influence customer service in this particular industry and regional setting. The importance of this study is rooted in its ability to deepen our comprehension of how servant leadership affects service quality, specifically within the context of Pakistan's fast food sector. By investigating the mediating role of service climate, it provides valuable insights that can guide leadership practices and organizational strategies in this specific context, ultimately leading to improved customer service experiences and potentially boosting the competitiveness of fast food chains. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of considering cultural nuances when applying leadership theories, contributing to not only the academic literature but also offering practical implications for businesses operating in similar industries and regions (Munarko, 2022).

The study "Examining the Impact of Servant Leadership on Service Quality: Exploring the Mediating Role of Service Climate in the Fast Food Chains of Pakistan" appears to have a research gap regarding the potential moderating factors that could influence the relationship between service climate, servant leadership, and service quality in the fast food industry. Understanding how external factors, such as market dynamics, customer expectations, or regulatory influences, may interact with these variables could provide a more comprehensive and nuanced perspective on the dynamics at play within this specific context and enrich the study's findings.

A comprehensive review in this field was carried out by Bavik (2020), who emphasised the benefits of servant leadership for organisations and employees in the hospitality sector. Furthermore, Chon and Zoltan (2019) developed a conceptual framework for servant leadership by analysing recent studies on hospitality and offering recommendations for future study areas.

Existing literature emphasizes the critical role of customer-centric values in enhancing the profitability of service organizations (Narver & Slater, 1990). However, for these values to be effective, they must be genuinely embraced and perceived by employees as part of the organizational culture. According to Schneider et al. (1998), service climate is the general opinion about practices, behaviours, and processes pertaining to quality and customer service. It is important because it reflects the importance of service inside an organisation (Yoon et al., 2001, p. 502). Human Resources Management (HRM) practices and management strategies are among the organisational elements that impact this climate (Little & Dean, 2006).

Literature Review

A pivotal aspect of services is their process-driven nature, emphasizing that service companies do not possess a tangible product; instead, they manage interactive processes. Services inherently lack visibility, making it challenging for both providers and consumers to assess (Ali et al., 2021). In the hospitality sector, which largely revolves around human interactions, the focus is placed on managing people, particularly the so-called "service encounters," which are exchanges between patrons and employees. The whole success or failure of a hospitality organisation is largely determined by the cumulative impact of these customer-driven service experiences (Abdullah, 2018).

Various scholars have proposed various definitions of what constitutes high-quality services. According to Saleh et al. (2021), service quality be defined as the discrepancy between the actual service that consumers receive and their expectations. Similar to this, Othman and Abdullah (2016) define service quality as the difference between a client's pre-interaction expectations and their post-interaction assessments. Gefan (2002), as referenced by Abdullah and Othman (2016), views

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service quality as the customer's specific judgment comparing their anticipated service quality with the actual service they receive. Defining quality is more complex than assessing customer satisfaction, as it is based on individual customer perceptions, implying that quality is essentially what the customer deems valuable (Abdullah & Abdul Rahman, 2015). Anwar and Abdullah (2021) point out consumer perceptions of service quality are influenced by two main factors: their expectations and the standards of quality. Expectations refer to what customers believe they will receive from a service provider (Anwar & Shukur, 2015).

A growing number of researchers are interested in service quality. According to a number of definitions, service quality determined by how well a service provider meets the expectations of its clients and how well they match their expectations (Anwar & Abd Zebari, 2015). Several research works have investigated the aspects of service quality that have a major impact on the basic evaluations of quality in service environments. Identifying these key factors is vital as it aids in measuring, managing, and improving perceived service quality (Anwar & Surarchith, 2015). One of the notable contributions in this area is by Parasuraman et al. (1985), who identified ten dimensions of service quality that form the basis of the SERVQUAL model:

An important study on bank branches found a noteworthy correlation: employees perceived a strong service climate in the branches that actively fostered facilitative conditions, such as efforts, supervisory behaviours, and HRM policies aimed at overcoming challenges and fostering positive interdepartmental relationships. Notably, consumers gave these branches good marks for the calibre of their services (Schneider et al., 1998). Subsequent studies that looked at ways to handle obstacles to employee performance provided more evidence for this association (Tesluk & Mathieu, 1999). Salanova, Agut, and Peiró (2005) highlighted critical elements for enhancing the service atmosphere in lodging facilities and dining establishments in the tourist sector. They found that, as first identified through qualitative approaches and then quantified in their study, organisational enablers such technical assistance, autonomy, and training were crucial in improving the service atmosphere. Customers' loyalty and opinions on the quality of the services they received were positively affected by this enhanced service environment. According to Davidson (2003), which is based on common views of the organisational environment, organisational climate, particularly service climate, is crucial for service quality (González-Romá, Lloret, & Peiró, 1995).

Subsequent research explored these concepts. For instance, organizational facilitators—which are meant to develop HRM practices—and climate—which encompasses organizational and service climate elements—were found to be positively correlated with favorable customer outcomes like satisfaction and loyalty in the automotive manufacturing sector, according to an analysis conducted on 351 small organizations (Rogg, Schmidt, Shull, & Schmitt, 2001). Therefore, the establishment of a service atmosphere that influences customers' opinions of service quality favorably depends heavily on organizational facilitators and climate. Boundary personnel in service organizations engage with clients as well as the organizational environment. These workers no longer serve clients individually; instead, they operate in groups or teams. This pattern emphasizes how crucial it is to assess service quality at the unit level in order to maintain consistency when comprehending the connections between different constructs and how those links affect service quality (Carmeli, 2008; Spreitzer, Cohen, & Ledford, 1999).

Three primary leadership focuses have been found by research on service climate: formal vs informal leadership, general versus service-oriented leadership, and the management of fundamental components versus transformative leadership. A robust service atmosphere is fostered

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in the first emphasis by paying attention to detail in service operations and managing critical service aspects effectively. Studies by Schneider et al. (2005) and Salvaggio et al. (2007), for example, demonstrate that leaders who are dedicated to enhancing service quality by removing obstacles to achievement, establishing high standards, setting an example, and providing required resources are successful in fostering a service-oriented environment.

According to the COR theory, individuals have a natural tendency to safeguard and sustain their personal resources for the sake of their overall well-being. In the research, servant leadership serves as a mechanism that aids in the preservation of employees' psychological and emotional resources. Servant leaders are renowned for their provision of support, empathy, and genuine care for their team members. This preservation of resources can, in turn, result in heightened job satisfaction, reduced burnout, and an overall enhancement in service quality within fast food chains.

Furthermore, by its inherent design, servant leadership involves the allocation of resources to employees in the form of support, opportunities for skill development, and increased autonomy. These resource allocations can lead to an improved state of well-being and motivation among employees, ultimately exerting a positive influence on service quality. The concept of service climate, explored as a mediating factor in the study, can be construed as a resource within the organizational context. A favorable service climate can play a pivotal role in cultivating a work environment that encourages resource acquisition and conservation. It promotes teamwork, collaboration, and the efficient utilization of available resources, thereby making a significant contribution to heightened service quality. Furthermore, the study's concentration on servant leadership and the mediating role of service climate can also be understood in terms of averting resource loss. Servant leadership practices are effective in mitigating resource depletion among employees, including the reduction of stress and emotional exhaustion, which can have a direct and positive impact on service quality. In essence, the study's exploration of how servant leadership practices influence service quality via the mediating effect of service climate aligns harmoniously with the fundamental principles of the Conservation of Resources theory. This underscores the paramount significance of both preserving and accruing resources in the workplace, thereby generating substantial implications for service quality within the fast food chains of Pakistan.

Service provision is a vital component of operations for fast food businesses (Vandenabeele 2007). Setting high-quality service as a top priority is crucial (Wagenheim and Reurink 1991), which frequently calls for the development of an integrated service system. Thus, it is especially important to create a service atmosphere in the fast food industry that encourages, supports, and rewards excellent service quality (Bentein et al. 2022).

Based on their direct experiences with the company's procedures and guidelines, it symbolizes the atmosphere and general attitude in which staff members recognize and value the organization's emphasis on providing high-quality services (Hong et al. 2013; Liao and Chuang 2007). It is imperative that staff feel appreciated, supported, and rewarded for their efforts in providing top-notch service in order to foster a positive service atmosphere. As a result, service climate shapes the work environment through social context and influences employee behaviour based on signals they receive (Schneider, White, and Paul 1998). When a large number of employees hold this view, it acts as a social-contextual cue, motivating people to work more and become more involved in delivering high-quality services (Bentein et al. 2022).

H1: Servant leadership is positively associated with hospitality employees' Service Quality.

H2: Servant leadership is positively associated with Services Climate.

H3: Services Climate mediators between servant leadership and Service Quality.

Theoretical Model

Research Design

The research methodology adopted for this paper is quantitative-method. We used random sampling technique to collect the data. This questionnaire aims to gauge perceptions concerning servant leadership behaviors.

Data collection

The study involved service employed in fast food chain within Lahore, Pakistan. To assemble our sample, we initially obtained a list of fast food chain from the Punjab Food Authority and established communication with the human resource managers at these establishments. During these discussions, we outlined our need for participation from frontline service employees in our research. It was crucial to emphasize to the participants that their responses would be exclusively used for research purposes, and we assured them of the confidentiality of their data. Subsequently, we distributed questionnaires to the employees as per the schedule provided by the HR managers. In order to facilitate electronic submissions, we also employed Google Forms. Information collected from various sources was meticulously organized in an Excel format. This Excel file was subsequently utilized for the ensuing analysis through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS SEM).

We received 185 responses, of which four were considered incomplete and therefore excluded from the final sample, resulting in 181 participants. The servant leadership scale, which consists of 14 items, was adopted from Ehrhart (2004). Subsequently, the SERVQUAL generic questionnaire was taken from Chagas (2000), and this adaptation was carried out in a systematic and coherent manner. Reliability, tangibility, security, empathy, and responsibility are the five characteristics of service quality that are evaluated using 22 questions in the original SERVQUAL scale. A three-item scale that was modified from Schneider and Bowen's work was also used to assess the service climate (1985).

Results

According to Hair et al. (2012) and Henseler et al. (2009), we use the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS SEM) technique in this study to carry out a two-phase analysis that includes an Assessment Model and a Measurement Model. The link between items/variables and their indicators is the main emphasis of the measurement model. We use Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to analyse both discriminant and convergent validity in order to determine the validity of the Measurement Model. Composite reliability, which is thought to be more useful than

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Cronbach's Alpha, is used to assess the model's dependability (Starkweather, 2012). Convergent and discriminant validity tests are used to establish construct validity.

According to Hair et al. (2014) criteria, each item is rigorously assessed for composite reliability with a minimum acceptable loading level of 0.50. The factor loadings for each item are detailed in Table 1, with all values exceeding the 0.50 benchmark, confirming composite reliability within the dataset. If an item's loading falls below 0.50, it is excluded, and the analysis is repeated to reevaluate the loadings. Figure 1 visually depicts the model, including its factor loadings. Table 1 also highlights item consistency, with all variables scoring above 0.7, indicating strong consistency among the items.

As per Bagozzi et al. (1991), our research comprehensively investigates discriminant and convergent validity, which are essential components of construct validity. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is used to verify convergent validity; according to Fernandes (2012) and Hair et al. (2017, 2011, 2014), an AVE value greater than 0.50 is required. The AVE values in Table 1 are 0.778, 0.542, and 0.546, all of which satisfy the necessary threshold and certify the convergent validity of our study.

Table 1 Reliability & Convergent Validity

Variable	Items	Factor Loading	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Service Quality	SC1	0.832	0.856	0.857	0.913	0.778
	SC2	0.912				
	SC3	0.899				
	SL1	0.729				
	SL10	0.681				
	SL11	0.713				
	SL12	0.728				
	SL13	0.748				
	SL14	0.732				
Servant Leadership	SL2	0.651	0.937	0.946	0.943	0.542
	SL3	0.696				
	SL4	0.783				
	SL5	0.724				
	SL6	0.752				
	SL7	0.808				
	SL8	0.77				
	SL9	0.772				
	SQL1	0.601				
Service Quality	SQL10	0.687	0.939	0.951	0.946	0.546
	SQL11	0.787				
	SQL12	0.645				
	SQL13	0.702				
	SQL14	0.703				

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SQL15	0.724
SQL16	0.726
SQL17	0.723
SQL18	0.771
SQL19	0.765
SQL2	0.615
SQL20	0.758
SQL21	0.733
SQL22	0.699
SQL3	0.656
SQL4	0.621
SQL5	0.621
SQL6	0.592
SQL7	0.663
SQL8	0.741
SQL9	0.713

Figure 1 Measurement Model

According to Hair et al. (2010), discriminant validity assesses how distinct one variable is from others in the study. To determine discriminant validity, we utilize the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) as a diagnostic tool, based on the methodology described by Henseler et al. (2015). The results of the HTMT assessment are displayed in Table 2. The HTMT Ratio readings are compared to the guidelines provided by Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2011). These guidelines state that, as advised by Gold et al. (2001), the HTMT ratio should ideally be below 0.85 (HTMT < 0.85) or, in some circumstances, under 0.90 (HTMT < 0.90). Nevertheless, the results of our investigation

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show that every number in Table 2 is higher than the 0.90 benchmark, which means that it does not match the optimal cutoff point that Gold et al. (2001) suggested.

Table 2 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	SC	SL	SQL
SC			
SL	0.756		
SQL	0.673	0.737	

In our study, we assess the possibility of Multicollinearity by examining the values of the variables. The presence of Multicollinearity is indicated if any variable shows a value greater than 5. However, as depicted in Table 3, all variable values are below the threshold of 5, thereby confirming that Multicollinearity is not a concern in our research.

Table 3 Multicollinearity VIF

	SC	SL	SQL
SC			1
SL		1	
SQL			

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Figure 2 Structural Model

Table 4 Path Analysis

Hypothesis	Relation	Beta	SD	T value	P values	LL	UL	Decision
H1	SC -> SQL	0.631	0.045	13.897	0.001	0.545	0.721	Supported
H2	SL -> SC	0.722	0.048	15.16	0.010	0.623	0.803	Supported
H3	SL -> PCSP	0.461	0.056	8.182	0.000	0.351	0.572	Supported

The relationships between the research variables are shown in this section. In addition to providing a thorough synopsis of the suggested correlations between the variables, Table 4 shows the outcomes of a route analysis carried out with SEM PLS. The findings validate the support for H1

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by showing a statistically significant association between Service Climate (SC) and Quality (SQL) ($\beta = 0.631$, $t = 13.897$; LL = 0.545, UL = 0.721). Likewise, there is strong evidence for H2 for Servant Leadership (SL) and Service Climate ($\beta = 0.722$, $t = 15.16$; LL = 0.623, UL = 0.804).

Furthermore, it is also demonstrated that Service Climate (SC) mediates between SL and SQL ($\beta = 0.461$, $t = 8.182$; LL = 0.451, UL = 0.572), taking into account all pertinent factors. As thus, it follows that every one of our theories is supported. Figure 2 provides an overview of the structural model assessment.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

According to Henseler et al. (2009), the R-squared (R²) statistic is used to measure the percentage of variance in a dependent variable that can be explained by a group of independent variables. Understanding this statistic is essential to appreciating the model's predictive ability. According to Hair et al. (2014) and Henseler et al. (2009), R² indicates how much of the variance in the dependent variable can be ascribed to the model's independent variables. Researchers interpret R² values differently. Chin (1998a) and Cohen (1988), for example, propose that an R² value of 0.02 indicates a poor explanatory power, 0.13 shows a moderate level, and 0.26 or above indicates a great explanatory power (Götz et al., 2010).

Furthermore, one of the most important metrics in structural equation modelling (SEM) for evaluating the model's quality is the coefficient of determination (R²). Researchers like Chin (1998a) and Cohen (1988) have established several criteria for R² values; values of 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75, respectively, indicate poor, moderate, and great explanatory power (Chin, 2010).

In our study, as shown in Table 5, the R² values for the variables are presented. Specifically, the constructs "Servant Leadership" and "Service Climate" together account for 51.9% of the variance in "Service Quality" (SQL), demonstrating a significant explanatory power in the model.

Table 5

R-square of Constructs

Construct	R ²	Effect
"Service Quality" (SQL).	0.519	Moderate

Discussion and conclusions

This study was conducted to investigate the relationship between servant leadership and service quality in Pakistani fast-food chains, with an emphasis on the function of service atmosphere as a mediating factor. The study's conclusions have shed light on a crucial relationship—one that is especially pertinent to the fast-food sector—between leadership style, workplace culture, and service quality.

Our results demonstrate a substantial and positive association between service quality and servant leadership, which validates Hypothesis 1. Servant leadership's fundamental characteristics, such as prioritizing the needs of individual team members, displaying empathy, and caring for employees, harmonize well with the service-oriented nature of fast-food establishments. These qualities enhance job satisfaction and reduce burnout among staff, ultimately contributing to heightened service quality. This result is consistent with the body of research that highlights the positive effects of servant leadership on worker satisfaction and, in turn, customer satisfaction.

Hypothesis 2, This provided good empirical support for the hypothesis that servant leadership and

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service atmosphere are significantly correlated. A key component of creating a service-oriented work environment is the service climate, which is defined as the collective views of organizational policies and practices on customer service and service excellence. Positive service environments in fast-food chains encourage collaboration, teamwork, and the effective use of resources, all of which improve the quality of the services provided.

Hypothesis 3, The research further established the mediating role of service climate in the relationship between servant leadership and service quality. Servant leadership practices create an environment that averts resource depletion among employees, reduces stress, and mitigates emotional exhaustion. Consequently, service climate serves as a vital intermediary, effectively translating servant leadership into enhanced service quality by facilitating resource preservation and accrual.

In conclusion, this study's outcomes have illuminated the symbiotic relationship between servant leadership, service climate, and service quality in the fast-food chains of Pakistan. These findings hold pragmatic implications for managers and leaders within this sector, underscoring the potential benefits of embracing servant leadership to improve service quality. Moreover, the promotion of a service climate that champions collaboration and resource efficiency can further enhance service quality outcomes.

Theoretical implications

This study significantly enriches the theoretical landscape of leadership and service quality, particularly within the context of the fast-food industry in Pakistan. It reinforces the notion that servant leadership is a potent leadership style, which prioritizes employee well-being and the cultivation of a service-oriented culture. The study accentuates the importance of the Conservation of Resources (COR) theory, underlining the role of servant leadership in preserving and enhancing employee resources. Moreover, by unveiling the mediating role of service climate, this research contributes to our understanding of how leadership practices can shape the work environment, fostering cooperation and efficient resource utilization. These findings advance servant leadership theory, service climate theory, and the broader leadership literature, providing insights into the intricacies of leadership and service quality in a dynamic and service-driven industry.

Practical implications

For practical applications, this study offers valuable guidance to leaders and managers in the fast-food industry and service organizations at large. It underscores the potential benefits of adopting servant leadership as a guiding philosophy for leadership development. By promoting a culture of support, empathy, and care for employees, organizations can enhance employee well-being, reduce burnout, and, in the process, elevate service quality. Furthermore, the emphasis on fostering a positive service climate highlights the importance of teamwork and cooperation in the workplace, ultimately leading to more efficient resource utilization and improved service quality. This study also calls for human resource management practices that align with servant leadership principles and service climate enhancement, ultimately contributing to a more satisfied and motivated workforce. In summary, the practical implications underscore the actionable steps leaders can take to enhance service quality by embracing servant leadership and nurturing a conducive service climate.

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In summary, this research has provided insightful information about the interplay of servant leadership, service ambiance, and service quality in Pakistani fast-food chains. The results underscore the significance of implementing a servant leadership approach in this sector, given its favorable impact on the workplace atmosphere, workforce welfare, and ultimately, service excellence. It was determined that the service climate had a key mediating function in this connection, highlighting its critical significance in influencing the outcomes related to service quality. These results have practical implications for fast-food chain managers and leaders in Pakistan, suggesting that a focus on servant leadership can lead to improved service quality. To enhance service quality, managers should promote a service climate that encourages teamwork, cooperation, and the efficient use of resources.

Limitations and future research

Future studies might examine how various organizational elements and leadership philosophies affect the calibre of services. A longer-term investigation could offer a more profound comprehension of how these connections have changed throughout time. Essentially, this study adds to the expanding body of research on leadership in the service sector by providing guidance on how to improve service quality in Pakistan's fast-food business.

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